

SOP Title	DNA extraction from bacterial cells using MasterPure kit		
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Table of Contents

1. Purpose	2
2. Definitions and Abbreviations.....	2
3. Related Documents.....	2
4. Risk Assessment.....	3
5. Procedure	4
5.1 Equipment and Reagents.....	4
5.1.1 Equipment required	4
5.1.2 Consumables required.....	4
5.1.3 Reagents required	4
5.1.4 Reagent preparation and storage	4
5.2 Initial considerations in the laboratory	5
5.3 Extraction.....	5
5.3.1 Before starting	5
5.3.2 Bacterial preparation.....	5
5.3.3 Precipitation of proteins and DNA	6
5.3.4 Additional lysozyme step for difficult to extract samples.....	7
6. Review History.....	7

1. Purpose

This protocol is for the extraction of high molecular weight bacterial DNA using the Lucigen MasterPure kit.

2. Definitions and Abbreviations

DNA	Deoxyribonucleic Acid
CL2	Containment Level 2
MSC	Microbiological Safety Cabinet

3. Related Documents

TRACS_RA009_Masterpure_DNA_RNA_purification Kit

4. Risk Assessment

<i>Hazard (Cause and Consequence)</i>	<i>Affected Groups</i>	<i>Existing controls (e.g., PPE...)</i>
<i>Biological Hazards</i>		
Cultures of potentially human-pathogenic bacteria (hazard group 2, E. coli and K. pneumoniae)	Laboratory staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPE (lab coat and gloves) to avoid any contact with the body. • All the processing carried out in a Class II MSC. • Any centrifugation steps use aerosol-sealed lid/bucket. • No use of needles/sharps during the sample processing to prevent injuries. • Laboratory workers are monitored by Occupational Health. • Refer to biological risk assessment for further information.
<i>Chemical Hazards</i>		
Tissue Cell Lysis Solution: skin irritant, serious eye damage, harmful to aquatic life	Laboratory staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPE (lab coat and gloves) to avoid any contact with the body. Safety glasses should be used when working outside Class II MSC.
2-Propanol: irritant and flammable	Laboratory staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Handle in a chemical fume hood with the usage of PPE when working with large volumes. • Aliquot into small working volumes (max 50ml)
Ethanol: flammable	Laboratory staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Handle in a chemical fume hood with the usage of PPE when with large volumes. • Aliquot into small working volumes of 70% (max 50ml)
Virkon Powder: irritant to eyes, skin and corrosive to metal.	Laboratory staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PPE (lab coat and gloves) to avoid any contact with the body. Safety glasses should be used when working outside Class II MSC. • Concentration to be used: 2% (no less than 1% final concentration when diluted).
Chemgene: corrosive, irritant to eyes and skin.	Laboratory staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Handled in a chemical fume hood with the usage of PPE when in high concentrations. • Once diluted it can be used to spray surfaces. • Final concentration to be used: 5%
<i>Physical Hazards</i>		
None	N/A	N/A

5. Procedure

5.1 Equipment and Reagents

5.1.1 Equipment required

Class II MSC	Heat block
Microcentrifuge	Variable speed rotator
Fume hood	
Thermomixer	

5.1.2 Consumables required

Materials	Company/Code
1.5ml microcentrifuge tubes	Fisher/3451
1000µl pipette tips (960)	Starlab/S1122-1830
200µl pipette tips (960)	Starlab/S1120-8810
20µl pipette tips (960)	Starlab/S1123-1810
10µl pipette tips (960)	Starlab/S1121-3810
50ml falcon tubes	Greiner/210261
5ml serological pipette	Greiner/606180
10ml serological pipette	Greiner/607180
25ml serological pipette	Greiner/760180
50ml serological pipette	Greiner/768180
1ul loops	Greiner/731165

5.1.3 Reagents required

Reagents	Company/Code
Tissue and Cell Lysis Solution	Cambio/MTC096H
Proteinase K	Cambio/MPRK092
RNase A	Cambio/MRNA092
Protein Precipitation Buffer	Cambio/MMP095H
TE buffer	Cambio/MTE0970
Isopropanol	Fisher/1190764
70% Ethanol	Collect from CTID facilities
Sterile PBS	Fisher/10010023
TRIS-HCl pH 8.0	Fisher/17926/320331
EDTA	Fisher/15575020
Triton-X-100	Merck/T8787
Sterile water	Merck/W3500

5.1.4 Reagent preparation and storage

Preparation of Lysis buffer + Proteinase K solution

- Prepare 300µl of Tissue and Cell Lysis Solution + 1µl of Proteinase K per sample to be extracted

- Mix well and use immediately.

Plate sweep samples may require 1.5µl of proteinase K per sample.

5.2 Initial considerations in the laboratory

- All the samples should be treated as potentially infectious until lysis has taken place. Therefore, samples must only be opened in a class II MSC until considered inactivated.
- The use of lidded, aerosol-tight centrifuge buckets is compulsory.
- Before starting, thoroughly clean the class II MSC with Chemgene (5% solution) and 70% ethanol. Switch the Class II MSC on and leave it running until airflow is safe
- For inactivation of liquid waste or to clean up small spills, use freshly prepared 2% Virkon solution in a 1:1 dilution with waste (no less than 1% Virkon final concentration). For waste containers, leave the Virkon for a minimum of one hour, ideally overnight, before diluting and disposing down the laboratory sink.
- All other solid waste is considered contaminated and must be disposed by autoclaving followed by incineration.

5.3 Extraction

5.3.1 Before starting

- Set the thermomixer to 65°C
- Set the heat block to 37°C
- Prepare lysis buffer and 70% ethanol
- Keep Proteinase K and RNase A on ice until needed.

5.3.2 Bacterial preparation

Liquid culture:

1. Take required volume of liquid culture (recommended 500µl-1ml) and transfer to a labelled 1.5ml microcentrifuge tube.
2. Centrifuge at 10,000 rpm for 3 minutes to pellet.
3. Discard the supernatant and resuspend in 500µl of sterile PBS.
4. Centrifuge at 10,000 rpm for 3 minutes to pellet.
5. Discard the supernatant, leaving approximately 25µl of PBS. Vortex for 10s to resuspend the pellet.
6. Add 300µl of pre-prepared lysis buffer + proteinase K solution and vortex to mix. Proceed to step 11.

Colonies from plates:

7. Using a 1µl loop, scrape a loop of colonies/single colony into 1ml sterile PBS.
8. Centrifuge at 10,000 rpm for 3 minutes to pellet.
9. Discard the supernatant, leaving approximately 25µl of PBS. Vortex for 10s to resuspend the pellet.
10. Add 300µl of pre-prepared lysis buffer + proteinase K solution and vortex to mix. Proceed to step 11.
11. Incubate at 65 °C for 15 minutes on the thermomixer shaking at 1000rpm (if using static heat block, vortex every 5 minutes). If samples do not appear clear after this step, vortex them and place back in thermomixer for 2-minute intervals, until clear.
12. Place the samples on ice for 3-5 minutes and then add 1µl of RNase solution to each sample.
13. Incubate at 37°C for 30 minutes in static heat block.
14. Place samples on ice for 3-5 minutes and then proceed with protein precipitation.

The samples are now considered inactivated and can be processed on the bench.

5.3.3 Precipitation of proteins and DNA

15. Add 150µl of Protein Precipitation Reagent to 300µL of lysed sample and vortex vigorously for 10 seconds.
16. Pellet the debris by centrifugation at 4°C for 10 minutes at 10,000 x g in a microcentrifuge. If the resultant pellet is clear, small or loose, add an additional 25µl of MPC Protein Precipitation Reagent, mix and pellet the debris again.
17. While the samples are being centrifuged, prepare a fresh, labelled 1.5ml microcentrifuge tube with 500µl of isopropanol.
18. Carefully pour or aspirate the protein precipitation supernatant into the isopropanol microcentrifuge tube and discard the pellet. Be careful not to disturb the pellet during this step. If the pellet is disturbed, re-centrifuge as in step 16.
19. Invert the tube 30-40 times (using the variable speed rotator).
20. Pellet the DNA by centrifugation at 4°C for 10 minutes at 10,000 x g in a microcentrifuge.
21. Carefully pour/aspirate off the isopropanol without dislodging the pellet.
22. Rinse the pellet twice with 100µl of 70% ethanol, being careful to not dislodge the pellet. Centrifuge briefly if the pellet is dislodged. Remove all of the residual ethanol with a pipette and leave tubes open for several minutes to allow the pellets to dry.

23. Resuspend the DNA in 50 µL of TE Buffer (for best results elute on the bench for ~1hr or overnight at 4°C). Following qubit quantification, freeze tubes at -20°C.

5.3.4 Additional lysozyme step for difficult to extract samples

If initial extraction protocol fails, an additional lysozyme digestion step can be added to the protocol prior to 5.3.2 step 1.

Preparation of Lysozyme solution (5ml)

Weigh out 100mg of lysozyme powder and resuspend in the solution below (total volume 5ml)

Reagent	Concentration	Concentration required	Volume
TRIS-HCl pH 8.0	1M	20mM	100µl
EDTA	0.5M	2mM	20µl
Triton-X-100	100%	1.2%	60µl
Water	N/A	N/A	4820µl

1. Prepare colony picks/liquid cultures as described in 5.3.2 but before adding lysis buffer + proteinase K, add 100µl of lysozyme solution and incubate tubes at 37°C for 15 minutes shaking at 1000 rpm.
2. Continue with protocol above from lysis step.

Lysozyme use recommended in plate sweep samples.

6. Review History

Correction of volumes and typos

19/08/2024 - Recommendation of volume of Proteinase K in plate sweep samples, and Lysozyme.